
OPTIMIZING PUBLIC EXPENDITURE FOR SUSTAINABLE WELFARE IN NIGERIA: PATHWAYS TO LONG-TERM IMPACT

Samuel Oladipo

Department of Economics, University of Lagos
osoladipo@gmail.com

Wisdom Okere* (corresponding author)

Department of Accounting, Bells University of Technology, Nigeria
wisescar@yahoo.com

Ajbola A. Akinyemi

Department of Economics, Bells University of Technology, Nigeria
ajibolayemi@gmail.com

Oraka F. Kesiena

Department of Economics, Bells University of Technology, Nigeria
kesiena.oraka@outlook.com

Jennifer David

Research student: Department of Economics, University of Lagos
jdavids@gmail.com

Abstract

This study explored the link between public expenditure and welfare sustainability in Nigeria, spanning from 1990 to 2022. We utilised several statistical analyses, encompassing descriptive statistics and Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) regression analysis. The Granger causality test showed significant unidirectional causal relationships between public expenditure and welfare. The FMOLS regression result showed that public expenditure on agriculture, education and construction has a strong positive and statistically significant effect on Nigerian welfare. However, public health spending shows a negative impact on welfare in Nigeria. In conclusion, the findings emphasize the opportunity to improve living standards and welfare in Nigeria by increasing government spending in key sectors. The study recommends augmenting agricultural allocations, enhancing education funding, introducing free primary healthcare, and promoting the Public-Private Partnership model in healthcare to foster sustainable development, welfare improvement, and poverty reduction in the country.

Keywords: Public Expenditure, Welfare, Sustainability, Nigeria, Poverty

1. INTRODUCTION

Public expenditure plays a crucial role in promoting human development and enhancing the overall well-being of a nation's population (Bhanumurthy et al., 2018). Governments have the opportunity to effectively utilize public funds to support economic growth and ensure long-term societal development. By prioritizing investments in key areas such as education, healthcare, infrastructure, affordable housing, environmental conservation, and the agricultural sector, governments contribute not only to economic prosperity but also to the quality of life for their citizens. These investments have the potential to reduce poverty, foster social welfare, and create positive outcomes for individuals and society as a whole (Saini and Mahender, 2023; Samuel and Oruta, 2021).

From a global perspective, public expenditure plays a crucial role in promoting human development and well-being, particularly in developing countries facing significant challenges such as poverty, inequality, and limited access to basic services (Singh and Chudasama, 2020). It is vital to align social security measures with a country's growth rate to ensure sustainable human development. Neglecting to provide adequate welfare support as the economy expands can impede progress in human development (Djukic and Biljana, 2020). Therefore, effective public expenditure is essential for creating an enabling environment that fosters human development and overall well-being.

In the specific context of Nigeria, there has been a consistent increase in public expenditure aimed at fostering economic development. However, despite the steady rise in government spending, largely driven by the country's crude oil wealth (Aregbeyen and Kolawole, 2015), Nigeria continues to face challenges such as low economic growth and a growing poverty rate. The substantial amount of annual public spending has not led to significant improvements in the health and overall well-being of the population. The unequal distribution of government resources is a key factor, with a significant proportion of Nigerians living in poverty and lacking access to essential public services such as healthcare and education.

Despite the arguments put forth by numerous scholars regarding the positive impact of increased government spending on economic growth, development, and the overall well-being of citizens (Hsu, 2013; Mafrolla and Amico, 2016; Ojo, 2020; Olaoye et al., 2020), the existing disparity between the anticipated outcomes and the actual situation experienced by the Nigerian population necessitates a comprehensive study. This research aims to thoroughly assess the effect of government expenditure on the welfare of Nigerians, addressing the gaps in previous research.

Upon reviewing the existing literature, it was observed that the majority of studies have primarily focused on examining the relationship between government spending and economic development in Nigeria (Saad and Kalakech, 2009; Taiwo and Abayomi, 2011; Stephen, 2012; Olabisi and Oloni, 2012). Only a few studies have explored the specific relationship between government spending and welfare, and even among these studies, discrepancies in findings arise due to variations in the choice of variables and analytical methods employed.

In light of the aforementioned, this research aims to make a valuable contribution to the existing knowledge by conducting a comprehensive analysis of the impact of government expenditure on welfare in Nigeria, with a specific focus on assessing its sustainability. Additionally, the study seeks to explore whether a causal relationship exists between different components of public expenditure and welfare in the country by utilizing secondary data from the period spanning 1990 to 2022. Through rigorous analysis and interpretation of the data, this research endeavour aims to provide valuable insights into the relationship and effectiveness of government expenditure on the welfare of Nigerians.

This paper comprises five sections designed to address the research objectives comprehensively: an introduction, literature review, theoretical framework and methodology, data analysis, and conclusion. The study's outcomes and recommendations aim to guide policy decisions and actions aimed at improving the influence of government expenditure on the well-being of the Nigerian population.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concept of Public Expenditure (Spending)

Public expenditure, also known as government spending, encompasses the costs borne by the government to sustain itself and provide societal benefits, financed through taxation and other means. It can be classified into two primary categories: recurrent expenditure, which covers day-to-day operational costs, and capital expenditure, which involves investments in infrastructure and long-term projects (Tanzi and Schuknecht, 2000). Government spending plays a pivotal role in addressing challenges arising from population growth, demographic shifts, rising income levels, and changing preferences. As economies expand and living standards improve, there is a greater demand for government services and goods (Fan, 2008). Moreover, industrialization and technological advancements necessitate government investments to cater to the evolving needs of these sectors. Through strategic allocation of funds to areas such as education, healthcare, infrastructure, social security, and environmental conservation, governments can promote economic development, social welfare, and overall well-being. Effective resource allocation is crucial to ensure that public expenditure generates maximum benefits and contributes to long-term sustainable development (Fan, 2008).

The Concept of Welfare

The concept of welfare is closely intertwined with poverty, serving as a crucial measure of overall wellbeing. Various conceptual viewpoints have been established to understand poverty and welfare. One perspective defines poverty as the extreme lack of essential human needs at the individual or household level (Makdissi and Wodon, 2006). Another viewpoint describes poverty as the inability to achieve basic capabilities, including proper nutrition, balanced living, economic and social skills, and participation in community activities (Wagle, 2002). In the 1990s, a third conceptualization of poverty emerged, emphasizing subjective poverty evaluations, where the poor or their communities define poverty themselves (Robb, 2002). This approach originated from participatory assessments of rural initiatives and takes into account both the physical and psychological dimensions of poverty.

Poverty is commonly understood as a socioeconomic condition characterized by insufficient access to fundamental human needs, such as food, shelter, clean water, sanitation, education, and employment opportunities, necessary to maintain a socially acceptable minimum standard of living within a given community (Jazbec, 2022; Akintola and Yusuf, 2001). It represents a state in which individuals are unable to provide themselves and their families with the basic necessities of life due to economic, social, political, or psychological constraints. Overall, poverty serves as a significant indicator of well-being or welfare, and the different conceptual viewpoints provide valuable perspectives for understanding and addressing poverty-related issues (Akintola and Yusuf, 2001; Robb, 2002).

Theoretical Review

Government expenditure and its impact on welfare have been explored through various theories. This review focuses on two prominent theories: the Public Choice Theory (PCT) and the Trickle-Down Theory (TDT).

Public Choice Theory (PCT) examines how decision-makers in government, such as politicians and bureaucrats, make choices. It suggests that these individuals are driven by self-interest and aim to optimize their decisions based on the available knowledge (Mengiste, 2020). While they may claim to act in the public interest, their own interests often take precedence. Political considerations, such as increasing influence and staying in office, can influence public expenditure decisions, leading to a focus on short-term projects for immediate gains rather than long-term welfare maximization (Mengiste, 2020).

On the other hand, the Trickle-Down Theory (TDT) posits that redistributing wealth from the rich to the poor benefits society as a whole. According to this theory, when the wealthy invest their

additional wealth, the resulting economic gains "trickle down" to the less affluent members of society (Aghion and Bolton, 1997). Governments, therefore, allocate funds to sectors like infrastructure, education, healthcare, and subsidies for basic commodities, believing that these investments will improve overall welfare and reduce poverty. TDT proponents argue that such investments generate positive outcomes, benefiting a larger portion of the population and leading to poverty reduction (Sowell, 2013).

These theories offer contrasting perspectives on the relationship between government expenditure and welfare. PCT emphasizes the self-interest of decision-makers and the potential impact on long-term welfare due to political considerations. In contrast, TDT highlights the belief that promoting economic growth and investing in sectors with broad societal benefits can lead to improved welfare and poverty alleviation.

Review of Empirical Literature

Several articles have investigated the effects of government expenditure in Nigeria, focusing on economic growth and development, with only a limited number examining welfare impacts. Danladi et al. (2015) found that increased government spending did not lead to long-term prosperity, emphasizing the need for a public funding policy that supports poverty reduction and private sector-led development. Olabisi and Oloni (2012) explored the relationship between public spending compositions and economic development, revealing that spending on health and agriculture had a positive impact while spending on water and education had negative effects.

Onifade et al. (2020) examined the patterns and impact of government spending on real GDP growth rates, establishing a long-run relationship between public expenditure and economic growth, with both recurrent and capital spending positively associated with GDP growth. Odior (2011) analyzed the dynamic impact of government spending on well-being, highlighting the significance of reallocating funds to the health sector for substantial economic growth. Nurudeen and Usman (2010) observed negligible growth impacts from overall recurrent and capital expenditure, while transportation, connectivity, and health spending had positive effects on development, whereas education spending had a negative impact.

In a broader context, the study by Olaoye, et al., (2020) provided insights into the relationship between government spending and economic growth in the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS). Their findings indicated that the impact of government spending on economic growth depends on the nature of spending shocks, suggesting the importance of considering both expansionary and contractionary policies. Moreover, an inverted "U-shaped" relationship was identified, indicating the existence of an optimal level of government spending for maximizing economic growth in the ECOWAS region.

These studies shed light on the varying effects of government expenditure across different sectors and their implications for economic growth, development, and welfare in Nigeria and the broader ECOWAS region.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Model Specification

In order to develop a model that can capture the effect of government spending on welfare this research adapted the model of Egbide's (2015) model in which the effect of government spending on poverty reduction (as a proxy for welfare) was captured. Egbide's (2015) model is defined as:

$$POI = f(PAGR, PEDU, PHLT, PTCOM, PCNSTR, INF) \quad (1)$$

Where: POI = Poverty Index/incidence (Proxy for welfare); LAGR = Public Expenditure on Agriculture; PEDU = Public Expenditure on Education; PHLT = Public Expenditure on Health; PTCOM = Public Expenditure on Transport and Communication; PCNSTR = Public Expenditure on Construction; INF = Inflation Rate;

However, by modifying this model, this research will use the Human Development Index (HDI) as a measure of welfare. Using the HDI instead of the POI is justified because HDI offers a comprehensive view of welfare, focuses on long-term well-being, aligns with policy priorities, allows for global comparisons, and emphasizes future-oriented investments in human capital. Therefore the econometric model for this study will be:

$$HDI = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 PAGR_t + \gamma_2 PEDU_t + \gamma_3 PHLT_t + \gamma_4 PTCOM_t + \gamma_5 PCNSTR_t + \gamma_6 INF_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

Where: HDI = Human Development Index as a measure of Welfare.

Next, we log of the variables. The essence of this is that it gives approximate parameters that can be explicitly translated as elasticities, as well as improved goodness of fit (R^2), which may add to a higher model's explanatory capacity. Equation (1) is thus obtained by taking the natural logarithm of both sides:

$$LHDI = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 LPAGR_t + \gamma_2 LPEDU_t + \gamma_3 LPHLT_t + \gamma_4 LPTCOM_t + \gamma_5 LPCNSTR_t + \gamma_6 LINF_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Where: L = Natural Logarithm; ε = stochastic error term; γ_0 and γ_{1-5} represent the constant and parameters to be estimated respectively.

Each expenditure variable in equation (2) is expressed as a ratio of real gross domestic product per capita (GDP) for the sustainability model. As a result, the second model for this research is as follows:

$$LHCD = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 \frac{LPAGR_t}{GDP} + \gamma_2 \frac{LPEDU_t}{GDP} + \gamma_3 \frac{LPHLT_t}{GDP} + \gamma_4 \frac{LPTCOM_t}{GDP} + \gamma_5 \frac{LPCNSTR_t}{GDP} + \gamma_6 LINF + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

The a priori expectation for this model is that $\gamma_1 - \gamma_5 > 0$; $\gamma_6 < 0$. This means that public expenditure on health, agriculture, transportation, and communication, as well as education, is projected to have a positive effect on welfare. However, inflation is projected to have a negative impact on welfare.

Granger Model

A Granger causality analysis was needed in this study to examine the nature of causality between various public expenditures and the welfare of Nigerians. The Granger Model for this study is specified below:

$$HDI_t = Z_0 + \sum_{p=1}^n Z_p PAGR_{t-p} + \sum_{r=1}^n \epsilon_r PEDU_{t-r} + \sum_{e=1}^n \chi_e PHLT_{t-e} + \sum_{w=1}^n \psi_w PTCOM_{t-1} + \sum_{x=1}^n \pi_x PCNSTR_{t-x} + U_{1t} \quad (5)$$

Data Collection and Method of Analysis

In this study, we employed the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) method due to its ability to address potential endogeneity and serial correlation issues in regression analysis. Before conducting the FMOLS analysis, we conducted the Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root test to assess the stationarity of variables. For our analysis, we utilized the E-Views software program, which facilitated FMOLS estimation, descriptive and trend analysis and unit root tests. The data for this methodological research was sourced from the World Development Indicators (WDI), the CBN statistical bulletin, and UNDP, covering the years from 1990 to 2022.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

	HDI	PAGR	PEDU	PHLT	PTCOM	PCNSTR	INF
Mean	0.4799	27.9059	202.748	123.548	21.6939	66.2427	18.0847
Median	0.4840	22.4400	119.020	62.2500	18.5100	20.0600	12.8765
Maximum	0.5730	76.6000	646.750	423.330	90.0300	206.110	72.8355
Minimum	0.3230	0.2100	0.2900	0.1500	0.2400	0.4100	5.3880
Std. Dev.	0.0577	25.5991	211.518	136.906	21.0994	71.3813	16.1079
Skewness	-0.5246	0.5318	0.8410	0.9219	1.2496	0.7385	2.1990
Kurtosis	2.8749	1.9457	2.3880	2.5443	4.7136	2.1519	6.8264
Jarque-Bera	1.5352	3.0838	4.4049	4.9597	12.6256	3.9886	46.7278
Probability	0.4641	0.2139	0.1105	0.0838	0.001813	0.1361	0.0000
Observations	33	33	33	33	33	33	33

Source: Authors EViews Extraction (2023)

Table 4.1 presents a detailed summary of the descriptive statistics on poverty, public expenditure on key sectors (agriculture, education, health, transport and communication, and construction), and the inflation rate spanning 1990 to 2022. From the Table, the average HDI value during the specified period is 0.48 indicating the average welfare level of Nigeria. Also, the HDI data exhibits a marginal inclination towards negative skewness, suggesting a prevalence of time periods characterised by lower human capital development levels rather than higher ones.

Looking at Public spending, the allocation of public funds towards agriculture, referred to as Public Expenditure on Agriculture (PAGR), demonstrates a notable dedication to the agricultural industry, as evidenced by an average investment of 27.91 billion Naira. This highlights the significant economic significance of the sector. The data distribution of PAGR exhibits a positive skew, indicating a progressive rise in agricultural expenditure over time. Education, as indicated by Public Expenditure on Education (PEDU), emerges as the frontrunner with the highest mean expenditure of 202.75 billion Naira, thereby emphasising its utmost significance. The data distribution of PEDU demonstrates positive skewness, suggesting a progressive trend of increased expenditure on education over time.

The allocation of public funds towards healthcare services, known as Public Expenditure on Health (PHLT), demonstrates a prioritisation of this sector. On average, the amount spent on healthcare services amounts to 123.55 billion Naira. This allocation is reflective of the government's commitment to improving both the accessibility and quality of healthcare. The data distribution of PHLT also exhibits positive skewness, indicating a tendency towards higher healthcare expenditure. On the other hand, there is a noticeable disparity in the allocation of funds towards Public Expenditure on Transport and Communication (PTCOM), which falls short with an average expenditure of 21.69 billion Naira, despite its pivotal role in facilitating infrastructure development. The data distribution provided by PTCOM illustrates fluctuations in expenditure. Infrastructure development is a prominent focus area in the allocation of public funds, specifically through the Public Expenditure on Construction (PCNSTR), which has an average expenditure of 66.24 billion Naira. This investment underscores the significance of construction projects. The data distribution of PCNSTR displays positive skewness, indicating a tendency for values to increase over time.

Finally, the Inflation Rate (INF) exhibits a high level of volatility, with an average value of 18.08%. The distribution of INF exhibits a positive skewness, indicating the presence of periods characterised by higher inflation rates that have the potential to affect the overall economic stability.

Figure 4.1: Welfare (HCD) Trend in Nigeria (1990 – 2022)

Source: Authors EViews Extraction (2023)

The data on the Human Development Index (HDI), scaled from 0 to 1, in Nigeria from 1990 to 2022 reveals that in the early 1990s, Nigeria experienced relatively low human development, with the HDI hovering around 0.4. However, during the mid-1990s, there was a slight uptick in human development, and this trend continued into the early 2000s, with the HDI peaking in the year 2000 at 0.57. Subsequently, there was a gradual decline in human development levels, with occasional fluctuations, until around 2018, when a significant decrease occurred, marked by a substantial rise in the HDI. From that point onward, the HDI maintained a declining trajectory, indicating an overall decline in human development levels.

Figure 4.2: Inflation Trends in Nigeria (1990 – 2022)

Source: Authors EViews Extraction (2023)

Figure 4.2 illustrates the inflation trends in Nigeria spanning from 1990 to 2022. Over this period, Nigeria has experienced fluctuations in its inflation rate, reflecting various economic dynamics. Notably, the data reveals episodes of relatively low inflation in the early 1990s and around the mid-2000s. However, there are also instances of elevated inflation, with peaks in the mid-1990s, early 2000s, and more recently around 2020. These fluctuations may be attributed to a variety of factors,

including changes in monetary policy, external shocks, and domestic economic conditions. However, the overall trajectory suggests that inflation has been a persistent challenge for Nigeria over the years, impacting economic planning and stability.

Figure 4.3: Public Expenditure Trend in Nigeria (1990 – 2022)

Source: Authors EViews Extraction (2023)

Figure 4.3 provides an insightful visual representation of the trends in public expenditure in billion Naira from 1990 to 2022 across different sectors in Nigeria. Notably, Public Expenditure on Education (PEDU) consistently stands out with the highest expenditure levels throughout this period. In 2020, it reached its peak at an impressive 646.75 billion Naira. This trend underscores the government's unwavering commitment to prioritize education as a key driver of human capital development and national progress.

Following closely is Public Expenditure on Health (PHLT), which also exhibited substantial growth over the years. In 2020, health expenditure soared to 423.33 billion Naira, emphasizing the critical importance of accessible and quality healthcare services, especially in light of global health challenges.

In contrast, Public Expenditure on Agriculture (PAGR) maintains a relatively lower level of spending compared to education and health. While it experienced some fluctuations, the highest recorded expenditure in this sector was 76.6 billion Naira in 2020. This suggests a more restrained allocation to the agricultural sector, despite its significance in ensuring food security and rural development.

Public Expenditure on Construction (PCNSTR) displayed a steady and consistent increase in spending over the years, reaching its peak at 206.11 billion Naira in 2020. This upward trajectory reflects the government's emphasis on infrastructure development as a catalyst for economic growth and national development.

Lastly, Public Expenditure on Transport and Communication (PTCOM) exhibits fluctuations in spending, with the highest recorded at 44.42 billion Naira in 2020. These fluctuations may indicate varying priorities within the transport and communication sector, which plays a crucial role in fostering connectivity and facilitating economic activities.

It is worth noting that the similarity in the trends of all five variables demonstrates that public spending has been on the rise in Nigeria over the years. The peak expenditure levels in 2020 can be attributed to the global COVID-19 pandemic, which prompted many nations, including Nigeria, to increase public spending as a means to stimulate the economy. This response was crucial, especially

after the lockdowns that disrupted economic activities, leading to increased public investment to bolster recovery and resilience in the face of unprecedented challenges.

Table 4.2: Granger Causality Result

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
PAGR does not Granger Cause HDI	32	9.83700	0.0039*
HDI does not Granger Cause PAGR		2.53273	0.1224
PEDU does not Granger Cause HDI	32	4.12498	0.0515**
HDI does not Granger Cause PEDU		0.56436	0.4586
PHLT does not Granger Cause HDI	32	3.96561	0.0559**
HDI does not Granger Cause PHLT		1.48270	0.2332
PTCOM does not Granger Cause HDI	32	1.11005	0.3008
HDI does not Granger Cause PTCOM		4.24174	0.0485*
PCNSTR does not Granger Cause HDI	32	4.34887	0.0459*
HDI does not Granger Cause PCNSTR		2.37070	0.1345

Note: () (**) indicate significance at 1% and 5% respectively Source: Authors EViews Extraction (2023)*

The Granger causality results in Table 4.2 suggest unidirectional causality between public expenditure and welfare in Nigeria. Specifically, public expenditure on agriculture (PAGR) and construction (PCNSTR) Granger causes changes in the Welfare (HDI) at a significance level of 5% indicating that variations in PAGR and PCNSTR have predictive power for changes in HDI. Similarly, public expenditure on education (PEDU) and Health (PHLT) Granger causes HDI at a 10% significance level, suggesting that PEDU and PHLT can predict some level of changes in HDI. On the other hand, HDI does not Granger cause PAGR, PEDU, PHLT or PCNSTR, indicating that changes in HDI do not significantly predict variations in public expenditures. Lastly, the Granger causality tests for transportation and communication (PTCOM), and public expenditure showed a unidirectional causal relationship running from HDI to PTCOM, at a 5% level of significance levels.

Table 4.3: Summary Stationarity Test Result using PP statistic

Variable	PP test stat @Levels	P-value @Levels	PP test stat @1 st difference	P-value @1 st difference	Remark
POI	-1.710865	0.4164	-11.71945	0.0000	I(1)
PAGR	-1.419827	0.5603	-15.14545	0.0000	I(1)
PEDU	1.720829	0.9995	-4.196381	0.0026	I(1)
PHLT	2.045191	0.9998	-6.202188	0.0000	I(1)
PTCOM	-1.819587	0.3646	-7.658557	0.0000	I(1)
PCONSTR	-0.328060	0.9098	-8.888111	0.0000	I(1)
INF	-2.429224	0.1421	-4.579344	0.0010	I(1)
GDP	-0.638210	0.8481	-2.585847	0.0115	I(1)

Source: Authors EViews Extraction (2023)

The summary Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root test results in Table 4.3 reveal that all variables are stationary at first difference and non at levels (I(0)). When all variables are stationary at the first difference (I(1)), the appropriate analysis method is Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS). FMOLS is chosen because it effectively deals with cointegrated variables, addressing the challenges associated with non-stationary data and enabling reliable estimation of long-term relationships among the variables. However, a Johansen Co-Integration Test was also conducted to check for Long-run relationships among the variables.

Table 4.4: Johansen Co-integration Test

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Trace Statistic	Prob.	Max-Eigen Statistic	Prob.
None	199.0372	0.0000*	55.14200	0.0044*
At most 1	143.8952	0.0000*	43.99549	0.0172*
At most 2	99.89971	0.0000*	39.88460	0.0085*
At most 3	60.01511	0.0024*	27.99078	0.0444*
At most 4	32.02432	0.0273*	18.77488	0.1036
At most 5	13.24944	0.1060	8.295393	0.3495
At most 6	4.954047	0.0260*	4.954047	0.0260*

Trace test indicates 5 cointegratingeqn(s) at the 0.05 level
 Max-eigenvalue test indicates 4 cointegratingeqn(s) at the 0.05 level
 * Denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

Source: Authors EViews Extraction (2023)

The outcome of the Johansen co-integration test in Table 4.4 shows minimum of five (5) cointegrating equations exhibit statistical significance at the 5% significance level, as evidenced by the p-values of the Trace test while there were four (4) for the Max-eigenvalue test. These observations collectively underscore the presence of a lasting long-run relationship among the data series employed in this study.

Table 4.5: Fully Modified Least Squares Regression Result

Dependent Variable: LHDI				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LPAGR/GDP	0.472135	0.148735	3.174329	0.0040*
LPEDU/GDP	2.179722	0.303298	7.186738	0.0000*
LPHLT/GDP	-2.364748	0.328105	-7.207300	0.0000*
LPTCOM/GDP	0.067059	0.087576	0.765722	0.4510
PCNSTR/GDP	0.610782	0.139538	4.377156	0.0002*
LINF	0.042745	0.013533	3.158616	0.0041*
C	-1.392876	0.067534	-20.62477	0.0000*
R-squared	0.753886	Mean dependent var		-0.737937
Adjusted R-squared	0.694819	S.D. dependent var		0.126518
S.E. of regression	0.069892	Sum squared resid		0.122124
Long-run variance	0.001559			
Residual Diagnostic Tests			F-statistic	Prob.
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			0.547120	0.5857
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroscedasticity Test			0.551287	0.7645

Note: (*) (**) indicate significance at 1% and 5% respectively Source: Authors EViews Extraction (2023)

The FMOLS regression results in Table 4.5 demonstrate that public expenditure in Nigeria has generally had a positive impact on the welfare of Nigerians. The findings reveal that, with the exception of public expenditure on transportation and communication (PTCOM), all other categories of public spending have a statistically significant effect on the welfare of Nigerians. Specifically, an increase in public spending on agriculture (PAGR), education (PEDU), and construction (PCNSTR) is associated with a significant improvement in the welfare of Nigerians. However, a rise in public spending on health (PHLT) is linked to a significant reduction in welfare.

The R-squared value of 75.4% and the adjusted R-squared of 69.5% indicate that the explanatory variables account for over 69% of the total variation in welfare levels in Nigeria. This suggests that the model provides a reasonably good fit for explaining welfare variations. In terms of diagnostic tests, the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test yielded a p-value of 0.5857, indicating no evidence of serial correlation in the model. Similarly, the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroscedasticity Test produced a p-value of 0.7645, suggesting the absence of heteroscedasticity in the model.

Table 4.6 Ramsey RESET Stability Test

	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	0.263144	25	0.7946
F-statistic	0.069245	(1, 25)	0.7946
Likelihood ratio	0.091277	1	0.7626

Source: Authors EViews Extraction (2023)

The results of the Ramsey RESET Stability Test in Table 4.6 provide evidence that the model is stable and correctly specified, as indicated by the high p-values for both the t-statistic and F-statistic (0.7946). Similarly, the likelihood ratio also yields a relatively high p-value (0.7626), reinforcing the

conclusion that the model is stable and well-specified. Furthermore, the CUSUM test shown in Figure 4.4 suggests model stability as long as the curve does not cross the boundary lines.

Source: Authors EViews Extraction (2023)

Discussion of Findings

The study investigates the relationship between public expenditure and welfare development in Nigeria, focusing on the years from 1990 to 2022. Descriptive and trend analysis revealed a consistent increase in public spending on agriculture, education, health, transportation/communication, and construction during this period. The Granger causality analysis unveils significant unidirectional causal links between public expenditure and welfare indicators in Nigeria. These results imply that Nigeria should prioritize investments in agriculture, construction, education, and health, as these sectors demonstrate significant predictive power for enhancing the Human Development Index (HDI) in the country. This one-way causal relationship underscores the potential of these investments to drive sustainable development and improve the overall welfare of the Nigerian population. Additionally, recognizing the causal link from HDI to public expenditure on transportation and communication (PTCOM) suggests that as human development improves, there may be opportunities to strategically allocate resources to infrastructure development to further facilitate economic growth and welfare enhancement.

The FMOLS regression results of the study indicate that sustainable public expenditure in agriculture, education, and construction has a strong positive and statistically significant effect on Nigerian welfare. This suggests that increasing government spending on education, possibly by providing free primary education, can positively impact people's welfare and alleviate the financial burden on parents. Furthermore, boosting public spending on agriculture could raise the country's standard of living by generating employment and increasing food production, thereby reducing poverty and improving welfare. However, it is noteworthy that increased public health spending is associated with a reduction in welfare in Nigeria. This might be attributed to potential inefficiencies or misallocation of resources within the healthcare sector, leading to suboptimal outcomes despite higher expenditures. Addressing these inefficiencies and ensuring effective resource allocation in healthcare is crucial for improving overall welfare and reducing poverty in Nigeria.

These findings are in accordance with prior research conducted by scholars such as Olabisi and Oloni (2012), Oni and Ozemhoka (2014), Obi and Obi (2014), and Edeme et al. (2017), all of whom, in various ways, have identified a positive correlation between public expenditure and the welfare of the Nigerian population and the overall economy. Therefore, the study underscores the importance of

strategic investments in specific sectors to promote sustainable development and enhance the welfare of the Nigerian population, ultimately contributing to poverty reduction and economic growth.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study delves into the intricate relationship between public expenditure and welfare development in Nigeria, focusing on the years spanning from 1990 to 2022. The descriptive findings illuminate a consistent upward trajectory in public spending overtime. The Granger causality analysis uncovers substantial unidirectional causal links between public expenditure and welfare indicators within Nigeria. The FMOLS regression results fortify these findings, underscoring that sustainable public expenditure in agriculture, education, and construction yields a robust, positive, and statistically significant impact on Nigerian welfare. This underscores the potential for enhancing the standard of living and bolstering welfare in Nigeria through increased government spending in these critical sectors.

Based on these findings, the study puts forth several recommendations. Firstly, the government should consider augmenting agricultural allocations and ensuring the efficient utilization of land resources, beyond private ownership, while simultaneously granting youths access to farmland. Secondly, there is an urgent need for increased funding for education, aiming to meet or even surpass the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization's (UNESCO) recommended allocation of 26% of national expenditure. Thirdly, addressing the quandary of negative effects stemming from public health expenditure necessitates the establishment of initiatives like free primary healthcare, fostering the comprehensive welfare of the population. Lastly, the report advocates for the robust institutionalization of the Public-Private Partnership model within Nigeria's health sector, thereby bolstering its financial capabilities and facilitating improvements in healthcare delivery. These recommendations, when realized, hold the potential to steer Nigeria towards sustainable development, enriched welfare, and reduced poverty.

Availability of data statement

The data that support the finding of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Funding

This study did not receive any funding.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

REFERENCES

- Aghion, P., and Bolton, P. (1997). A theory of trickle-down growth and development. *The review of economic studies*, 64(2), 151-172.
- Akintola, J. O., and Yusuf, J. (2001). Socio-economic analysis of poverty levels among rural dwellers in Kwara state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Environment and Development*, 5(2), 42-48.
- Aregbeyen, O., and Kolawole, B. O. (2015). Oil revenue, public spending and economic growth relationships in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 8(3), 113.
- Barro, R. J. (1990). Government spending in a simple model of endogenous growth. *Journal of political economy*, 98(5, Part 2), S103-S125.

- Bhanumurthy, N. R., Prasad, M., and Jain, R. (2018). Public expenditure, governance and human development. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 53(14), 36-46.
- Danladi, J. D., Akomolafe, K. J., Olarinde, O. S., and Anyadiegwu, N. L. (2015). Government expenditure and its implication for economic growth: evidence from Nigeria.
- Davoodi, H., and Zou, H. F. (1998). Fiscal decentralization and economic growth: A cross-country study. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 43(2), 244-257.
- Djukic, G., and Biljana, I. L. I. C. (2020). Sustainable development, social protection and responsibility. *İzmir Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 2(2), 83-91.
- Edeme, R. K., Nkalu, C. N., and Ifelunini, I. A. (2017). Distributional impact of public expenditure on human development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 44(12), 16831693.
- Egbide, B. C. (2015). Public budgeting and poverty reduction in Nigeria. *A Thesis Submitted to Covenant University CUGP070187*.
- Fan, S. (2008). *Public expenditures, growth, and poverty in developing countries: Lessons from developing countries* (No. 51). International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI).
- Hsu, Y. C. (2013). The efficiency of government spending on health: Evidence from Europe and Central Asia. *The Social Science Journal*, 50(4), 665-673.
- Jazbec, M. (2022). Diplomacy and management: in a search of an intersection in the time of globalisation. *International Journal of Diplomacy and Economy*, 8(2), 209-221.
- Koopmans, B. N. (1965). Structural evidence for a Palaeozoic orogeny in northwest Malaya. *Geological Magazine*, 102(6), 501-520.
- Mafrolla, E., and D'Amico, E. (2016). Does public spending improve citizens' quality of life? An analysis of municipalities' leisure supply. *Local Government Studies*, 42(2), 332-350.
- Makdissi, P., and Wodon, Q. (2006). Defining and measuring extreme poverty. In *Dynamics of inequality and poverty* (pp. 325-340). Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- Mengiste, B. W. (2020). Public choice theory: Its application and challenges in public sector. *Public Choice*, 66. Nurudeen, A., and Usman, A. (2010). Government expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria, 1970-2008: A disaggregated analysis. *Business and Economics Journal*, 4(1), 1-11.
- Obi, Z. C., and Obi, C. O. (2014). Impact of government expenditure on education: The Nigerian experience. *International Journal of Business and Finance Management Research*, 2(2104), 42-48.
- Odior, E. S. (2011). Government expenditure on health, economic growth and long waves in a CGE micro-simulation analysis: The case of Nigeria. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*, 31(1), 99-114.
- Ojo, A. E. (2020). The socio-economic drivers of public infrastructure development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Critical Infrastructures*, 16(4), 328-341.
- Olabisi, A. S., and Oloni, E. F. (2012). Composition of public expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, 3(4), 403-407.

- Olaoye, O. O., Eluwole, O. O., Ayesha, A., and Afolabi, O. O. (2020). Government spending and economic growth in ECOWAS: An asymmetric analysis. *The Journal of Economic Asymmetries*, 22(C).
- Oni, A., and Ozemhoka, M. (2014). Impact of public expenditure on the growth of the Nigerian economy. *European scientific journal*, 10(28).
- Onifade, S. T., Çevik, S., Erdoğan, S., Asongu, S., and Bekun, F. V. (2020). An empirical retrospect of the impacts of government expenditures on economic growth: new evidence from the Nigerian economy. *Journal of Economic Structures*, 9(1), 1-13.
- Robb, C. M. (2002). *Can the poor influence policy? Participatory poverty assessments in the developing world*. World Bank Publications.
- Romer, P. M. (1986). Increasing returns and long-run growth. *Journal of political economy*, 94(5), 1002-1037.
- Samuel, U. D., and Oruta, I. L. (2021). Government expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria: A disaggregated analysis. *Path of Science*, 7(11), 4022-4035.
- Saini, M., and Mahender. (2023). Surviving crisis: the role of sustainable investments in navigating the impact of the Russia-Ukraine war. *International Journal of Diplomacy and Economy*, 9(2), 189-204.
- Singh, P. K., and Chudasama, H. (2020). Evaluating poverty alleviation strategies in a developing country. *PLOS ONE*, 15(1), 1-23.
- Solow, R. M. (1956). A contribution to the theory of economic growth. *The quarterly journal of economics*, 70(1), 65-94.
- Sowell, T. (2013). *Trickle Down Theory" and" Tax Cuts for the Rich* (No. 635). Hoover Press.
- Tanzi, V., and Schuknecht, L. (2000). *Public spending in the 20th century: A global perspective*. Cambridge University Press.
- Wagle, U. (2002). Rethinking poverty: definition and measurement. *International Social Science Journal*, 54(171), 155-165.
- World Bank. 2023. World Development Indicators database. Washington, DC. <http://data.worldbank.org>.